

A STUDY ON DESIGN PROCEDURE OF FOAM CORE SANDWICH PANEL JOINT BASED ON FRACTURE MECHANICS

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1 Introduction

Fundamental researches on the application of co-cured CFRP face/ foam core sandwich panels to aircraft structure have been conducted [1,2]. In these researches, Hirose *et al.*[1] reported that, if co-cured CFRP face/ foam core sandwich panels were applied to aircraft structure, especially to the complexly curved surface portion such as nose fuselage structures, structural weight and part count could be significantly reduced. In this application, a panel joint is an inevitable structural element because of the restriction of production facilities of the sandwich panel. For the configuration of the panel joint, Hirose *et al.*[2] proposed a butt type joint. In this joint, sandwich panel which consists of face plates and foam core is tapered to form the solid laminate of two face plates near the joint portion and two panels to be joined are mechanically fastened at the solid laminate portions with a splice plate. Hirose *et al.*[2] conducted the tensile strength test utilizing the test piece of the butt type joint and reported that the delamination crack initiating from tapered core end and propagating through interface between two face plates were observed as an initial failure mode.

If design parameters such as angle of tapered panel portion and thickness or stacking sequence of CFRP face plates are adequately selected, propagation of delamination crack initiating from tapered core end could be restrained. In this study, angle of tapered panel portion, which is one of the design parameters for the butt type joint, is focused on and relations between the taper angle and the energy release rate of the delamination crack are investigated based on the finite element analysis. Then, in the light of the suppression of the delamination crack propagation,

how to design the taper angle of the joint is discussed.

2 Analysis

2.1 Description of the sandwich panel joint

The configuration of the butt type joint is shown in Fig.1. Sandwich panel which consists of CFRP face plates and foam core is tapered to form the solid laminate which consists of two face plates near the joint portion and two panels to be joined are mechanically fastened at the solid laminate portions with an aluminum splice plate and titanium bolts. The placements of the panel joints in aircraft fuselage structure are also shown in Fig.1. In this study, the joint which connects two sandwich panels placed along fuselage longitudinal direction is called the longitudinal joint. And the joint between two panels placed along circumferential direction is called the circumferential joint.

Fig.1 Configuration of butt type joint.

2.2 Finite element model of the joint

Hirose *et al.*[2] conducted the static tensile test using the butt type joint test piece and reported that the delamination crack initiating from tapered core end and propagating through interface between two face plates (see Fig.2) occurred as an initial failure mode.

Fig.2 Delamination crack initiating from tapered core end.

In this study, finite element model of the panel joint is prepared and the relations between the taper angle of the core and the energy release rate of a delamination crack are examined. Specifications of the sandwich panel and the joint are determined based on the test piece utilized by Hirose *et al.*[2]. Face plates consist of 16-ply graphite/epoxy twill weave fabric composite (UT500/#135, Resin content = 35%) laminates with nominal thickness of 6.24 mm. The ply orientations of the laminate are $[\{(+45,-45)/(0,90)\}_4]_{sym}$. The resin content of two plies which is adjacent to the foam core was increased from 35% to 45% to enhance the adhesion between prepreg and core. PEI (polyether imide) foam constitutes the core. The thickness of the core is 34mm in the sandwich panel portion and is reduced gradually to 0mm at the solid laminate portion. Resin films with thickness of 0.254mm are inserted between the face laminate and the foam core. These resin films are extended by 5mm to the solid laminate portion from the tapered core end. The thickness of the aluminum splice plate is 8mm. The splice plate is installed by titanium bolts with the diameter of 7.92mm and the spacing of 32 mm.

Fig.3 shows the 2-dimensional finite element model of the longitudinal joint. Taking the symmetry and the periodicity into considerations, finite element model for half of the longitudinal panel span is prepared. Face plates, core and resin

films are modeled by 4-node plane strain elements. Beam elements are utilized to model the splice plate and the fastener bolts. Mechanical properties of the constituent materials utilized in the analysis are shown in Table.1 and 2. For the circumferential joint, the same finite element model as that of the longitudinal joint is utilized, but the model is configured to have short panel span.

Fig.3 Finite element model of butt type joint.

Table 1 Mechanical properties of constituent plies of CFRP face plates²⁾.

	CFRP (0,90) RC=35%	CFRP (+45,-45) RC=35%	CFRP (0,90) RC=45%	CFRP (+45,-45) RC=45%
E_{11} [GPa]	66.3	15.1	54.9	12.6
E_{22} [GPa]	8.61	8.61	8.61	8.61
G_{12} [GPa]	3.77	3.31	3.77	3.31
ν_{12}	0.331	0.331	0.331	0.331
G_{13} [GPa]	4.24	31.6	3.53	26.1
G_{23} [GPa]	3.77	3.31	3.77	3.31

1: In-plane longitudinal direction

2: Thickness direction

Table 2 Mechanical properties of core and resin film²⁾.

	PEI foam core	Resin Film
E[GPa]	0.0275	2.41
G[GPa]	0.0110	1.03
ν	0.250	0.167

When the sandwich panels are applied to the airplane nose fuselage structure, cabin pressure load is primarily applied to the panel and joint portion. To estimate the cabin pressure load, it is assumed that the aircraft flies at an altitude of 10670m (35000ft) where the atmospheric pressure is 265hPa (0.26atm) and that the cabin pressure is maintained at 748hPa (0.74atm) which is equal to the atmospheric pressure at an altitude of 2438m (8000ft). Thus, the differential pressure between outer and inner sides of the cabin is assumed to be 483hPa (0.48atm). In the analysis of the circumferential joint, only hoop tensile load due to the cabin pressure is applied to the analysis model. While, for the longitudinal joint, the differential cabin pressure load directly applied to the sandwich panel as well as the fuselage longitudinal tensile load due to the cabin pressure which is equal to half of the hoop tensile load is taken into considerations. To estimate the hoop tensile load and the longitudinal tensile load, the diameter of the aircraft fuselage is assumed to be 5.74 m. Fig.4 and Table 3 show the loading conditions for longitudinal and circumferential joints.

Fig.4 Schematic representation of loading conditions for longitudinal and circumferential joints.

Table 3 Loading conditions for longitudinal and circumferential joints.

	Longitudinal joint	Circumferential joint
Direct pressure load	483 hPa	/
Tensile load	Longitudinal tension 69.3 kN/m	

In order to investigate the relations between angle of tapered panel portion and energy release rates of a delamination crack, finite element models with various taper angles which have the same overall panel thickness are prepared. For the longitudinal joint, finite element models with various panel spans along fuselage longitudinal direction are also prepared. The energy release rate of the delamination crack is calculated utilizing virtual crack closure method [3]. An initial delamination crack which initiates from tapered core end and propagates through interface between two resin films and goes into the solid laminate portion with the length of 2mm is included in the analysis model (Fig.5).

Fig.5 Finite element model of delamination crack.

3 Results

Fig.6 shows the relation between the taper angles and the energy releases rate of the delamination crack for the longitudinal joint when the longitudinal panel span is 1.0m. In Fig.6, results under two different loading conditions are presented. One

loading condition included only the longitudinal tensile load due to the cabin pressure and another condition comprised both the cabin pressure load directly applied to the sandwich panel and the longitudinal tensile load due to the cabin pressure. Fig.6 shows that, in the range of taper angles from 10 to 45 deg, the energy release rate becomes higher when both of the longitudinal tensile load and the panel pressure load are applied compared to the case when only the longitudinal tensile load is applied. Thus, the pressure load directly applied to the sandwich panel as well as the longitudinal tensile load should be taken into considerations when evaluating the energy release rate at the delamination crack tip for the longitudinal joint. Moreover, Fig.6 shows that there exists a taper angle which minimizes the energy release rate when both of the longitudinal tensile load and the panel pressure load are applied. This fact leads to the optimum design of the taper angle for the longitudinal joint in the light of the suppression of the delamination crack propagation.

Fig.6 Energy release rate at various taper angles with / without pressure load for longitudinal joint.

Next, Fig.7 shows the results of the longitudinal joint when the longitudinal panel spans are changed from 1.0 to 1.5m. In the analysis of the longitudinal joints, both of the pressure load directly applied to the panel and the longitudinal tensile load were taken into considerations. In Fig.7, the results of the circumferential joint are also presented. For the circumferential joint, the analysis was conducted

using the same finite element model as that utilized for the longitudinal joint with the panel span of 1.0m, and only the hoop tensile load was included in the loading condition.

Fig.7 Relations between energy release rate and taper angle for longitudinal joint with various panel spans and for circumferential joint.

It is observed from Fig.7 that, as the longitudinal panel span becomes larger, the energy release rate of the longitudinal joint becomes larger and the smaller taper angle minimizes the energy release rate. Moreover, for the longitudinal joint with longer panel span, the energy release rate decreases more rapidly with the decrease of the taper angle, though the decreasing tendency becomes gradual when the taper angle becomes 15deg or less. Thus, for the longitudinal joint, it is shown that the taper angle around 10 to 15deg is preferred to restrain the crack propagation, though the rigorously optimum taper angle is varied with the longitudinal panel span. On the other hand, for the circumferential joint, it is observed from Fig.7 that the energy release rate sharply decreases with the decrease of the taper angle especially in the range of taper angles less than 30deg. Thus, for the circumferential joint, the smaller taper angle will be effective to restrain the crack propagation.

4 Conclusions

In this study, for a butt type joint between two foam core sandwich panels, relations between taper angles of tapered part of the panel and energy release rates of a delamination crack initiating from tapered core end and propagating through interface between two face plates joined together are investigated based on finite element analysis. Assuming that the foam core sandwich panels will be applied to the aircraft fuselage structure, a longitudinal joint which joins two panels placed along longitudinal direction of the fuselage and a circumferential joint which joins two panels along circumferential direction are examined. Through the numerical investigations, followings are clarified:

- (1) For the longitudinal joint, there exists a taper angle which minimizes the energy release rate of the delamination crack. The taper angle around 10deg to 15deg is preferred to restrain the crack propagation, though the rigorously optimum taper angle is varied with the longitudinal panel span.
- (2) For the circumferential joint, the energy release rate of the delamination crack sharply decreases with the decrease of the taper angle especially in the range of taper angles less than 30deg. The smaller taper angle will be effective to restrain the crack propagation.

References

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